

Laser Pointer Detection using Image Processing For Telepointer System

Algoritma Pemprosesan Imej Untuk Penunjuk Laser Dalam Sistem Telepenunjuk

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ABSTRACT

Telepointer is a part of the teleconsultation system and its function is to capture the image and send the real time image to a medical expert that is located at another location. Telepointer makes use of a laser pointer as an indicator to make the communication easier between the users of this system. A laser pointer is a low cost and easy to obtain item that can easily attract someone's attention but providing a prominent spot on the region of interest. However, the ability of the system to detect the accurate position from the image captured was always the critical problem that the developer encountered for years. The laser spot seemingly easy to distinguish from its surrounding using bare eyes but it is not that easy for the system to track it. Therefore, the main goal of this study is to develop a new algorithm with high accuracy to detect the laser spot. In this study, a faster Region Convolutional Neural Network (faster-RCNN) has been used for laser spot detection. Besides that, an algorithm on the general image processing process was also developed as the ground truth data for training and validation of the faster-RCNN. There are 400 images in the dataset that were used to train the network and 100 images were used for validation. The results obtained from the network were compared with the ground truth data to analyze the performance of the trained network. To obtain a more robust result, a 5-fold cross validation was used. As a result, the average precision from all the 5 trained networks is 0.75.

Keywords: Object Detection; Faster-RCNN

ABSTRAK

Telepenunjuk adalah salah satu bahagian yang penting dalam sistem Teleperundingan dan berfungsi untuk menangkap dan menghantar imej secara masa nyata kepada pakar perubatan yang berada di tempat lain. Telepenunjuk menggunakan penunjuk laser sebagai penunjuk pada badan manusia untuk memudahkan komunikasi antara pengguna sistem ini. Penunjuk laser adalah sejenis alat yang kos rendah serta mudah diperolehi di pasaran dan alat ini dapat menarik perhatian seseorang apabila laser ditunjukkan pada tempat yang diingini. Namun, ketepatan sistem ini untuk mengesan lokasi penunjuk laser adalah masalah yang amat kritikal untuk mempengaruhi prestasi keseluruhan sistem ini. Walaupun penunjuk laser mudah dibezakan daripada objek lain dengan mata manusia, tetapi tidak begitu mudah dibezakan oleh mesin. Oleh itu, matlamat utama kajian ini adalah membangunkan algoritma yang lebih berkesan dalam mengesan lokasi penunjuk laser. Dalam kajian ini, Faster Region Convolution Neural Network (Faster-RCNN) telah digunakan sebagai algoritma utama. Di samping itu, algoritma pemprosesan imej umum turut dibangunkan sebagai data kebenaran untuk melatih dan pengesanan rangkaian Faster-RCNN. 400 imej telah digunakan sebagai dataset untuk melatih rangkaian dan 100 imej digunakan untuk pengesanan rangkaian. Keputusan yang didapatkan dari rangkaian Faster-RCNN akan dibandingkan dengan data kebenaran yang didapati daripada proses pemprosesan imej umum untuk menganalisis prestasi rangkaian yang dilatih. Untuk mendapatkan keputusan yang lebih kukuh, pengesanan silang 5 kali telah digunakan. Akhirnya, ketepatan purata yang didapati daripada 5 rangkaian yang dilatih adalah 0.75.

Kata Kunci: Pengesanan Objek; Faster-RCNN

INTRODUCTION

Teleconsultation is a long distance communication system to deliver medical care between a subspecialist and a patient or medical person using some kinds of communication method such as voice call or shared image, medical record, video, synchronously shared remote mouse pointer and on-screen drawing capabilities, etc. (Zhang et al. 2000). Teleconsultation is a type of computer supported cooperative work (CSCW) and creates consistency in availability of health care across geographical distance. Therefore, this system tends to alters hospital amenities to community and home centred facilities. Studies have proven teleconsultation is a dependable and economical way of delivering valuable medical care. (Verhoeven et al. 2007) This system had been widely used in almost all medical fields such as neurology, nursing, radiology, diabetic care and etc. Teleconsultation had been started being practiced globally and various kind of research are ongoing to further improve related technology to various field of telemedicine (Parikh, Sattigeri & Kumar 2014)

Teleconsultation are make out of few parts such as a Telepointer and the main parts of a Telepointer is the laser pointer in it. Figure 1 shows a teleconsultation setup including a laser pointer as telepointer. A laser pointer is a device built by a power source or typically a battery and a laser diode emitting a low-powered coherent visible light. This light can be easily distinguishable by the human bare eye and acts as a highlighter to draw focus. It is a low-cost device that widely used in our daily life that can be used to highlight something or spot of interest by pointing the laser light on it. The common laser pointer has three primary colours, red, green and blue. A green laser is a more appropriate choice due it distinguishability from blood and tissue. Beyond of that, the uses of telepointer in teleconsultation system create a prospect of drawing a user's focus precisely to an important location by pointing remotely and thus it is way more efficient than lengthy voiced explanations or inefficient visuals to achieve the same results.

Figure 1. The General Setup of a Teleconsultation System

Source : Karim et al. 2013

There are few different area of studies been carried out on teleconsultation. Different attempts have been made to particularly identify the laser pointer in the image. The detection seemingly easy for a human to distinguish the laser point and the surrounding but it aren't easily for a machine anyway due to glare. A simple detection algorithm where the authors used colour thresholding in HSV format was proposed by Widodo, Chen & Matsumaru 2012. This algorithm works by identifying the pixels of a certain color, the color will be classified as laser point when the laser pointer color fall beyond a threshold value. This studies assume that laser light always have a greater pixels than its surrounding. Besides that, a two-step method was proposed by Olsen & Nielsen 2001 whereas they uses colour thresholding followed by a convolution filter. When colour thresholding are unable to identify the laser spot, convolution filter will be applied. However, this method has limited result and convolution filter process will take a long time. Some works had been done to achieve detection in real indoor environment, a three step algorithm was presented by Chávez et al. 2012 using template matching and dynamic umbrallization(TM+DU). This algorithm used template matching best match to obtain a dynamic threshold for the image by referring to the histogram properties. This algorithm shows a good results however it limited to a static image only. Widodo, Chen & Matsumaru n.d. proposed an algorithm with combined improvement on hardware and multistep software methods. He used a camera filter to enhance the characteristic of laser pointer in the image, then obtain the threshold for each image frame based on highest intensity pixel in grey scale. The threshold obtained is used to classify laser pointer pixels.

On the other hand, there are several attempts made for object detection using Deep Neural Network method. Girshick et al. 2014 proposed an

object detection algorithm with Region Convolutional Neural Network that consists of 3 modules. The first module function as generates a category-independent region proposals and second module is made up of large convolutional neural network that extracts a fixed-length feature vector from each proposed region from first module. Last module is a set of class specific linear SVMs. This study it trains CNNs end-to-end to make classification on the proposal regions into particular object categories or background. Another study by Ren et al. 2015 had proposed a Faster Region Convolutional Neural Network (Faster-RCNN) by using Region Proposal Networks(RPN) that shares whole image convolutional features with the network of detection.

A common scenario in teleconsultation is that a specialist is remotely providing guideline and leading healthcare of a patient. Based on studies, in a face to face teleconsultation, gestures produced by a leading medical expert can efficiently increase the interaction.(Sachpazidis et al. n.d.) However, teleconsultation isn't perfect now in many aspects. As discussed earlier, this system required a real time image communication to prevent any unexpected accident to happens, therefore telepointer are particularly important to make sure it have high accuracy on detecting the laser spot since any misleading will lead to miscommunication. Therefore, this study had been carried out to obtain an algorithm to detect the laser pointer.

METHODOLOGY

Two algorithm was developed in MATLAB. This sample set is needed for training as well as validate the neural network. The sample sets consisting of 500 images that took under a controlled environment. 500 images in this sample set consisting similar images but with laser pointer on the different spot in the image. The example of the image was shown in Figure 2. Before this set of sample data used in neural network, it will undergoes few general image processing process to obtain the coordinate of the laser spot in the each image.

Figure 2. The Example Of The Image Used In This Study

The general image processing was developed based on the normal procedure of image processing in which it generally involves 4 steps as shown in the Figure 3. The first step of image processing is image preprocessing. The main goal of this process is to make improvement of the image data that suppresses unwilling distortions or enhances the important features in the images for further processing. In this study, intensity image had been converted to a double precision image. This conversion make no changes on the appearance of the image while it convert the pixel of the image into the range of 0 to 1 only. The pixel in the double precision image was calculated by using the formula

Figure 3. The General Processes Involved In Image Processing

$$\text{pixel}_{\text{double}} = \frac{\text{pixel}_{\text{rgb}}}{255}$$

After that, the image will be undergo normalization to rescale the image to an interval of [0,1]. As we know that all the image are make out of 3 primary color which is Red, Green and Blue(RGB) with the equation $I_{\text{rgb}} = (F_r(x,y), F_g(x,y), F_b(x,y))$. So the input image were converted into 3 primary color image which is Red Image, Green Image and Blue Image. By inspection, we note that the laser spot are more obvious and easier to be distinguish in green image. Therefore, green image are used for image segmentation which is the second steps in image processing.

The main goal of image segmentation is to divide an image into multiple parts with respect to their neighbor characteristic. Besides that, this process also used to locate objects and boundaries in images. Thresholding segmentation was used in this study, the green image was undergoes binarization with threshold value 0.75. Threshold value plays an important role in this process, as it act as a border line for a pixel to be identify as white spot or black spot. If the pixel value is less than 0.75, it will be converted to 0 or a black spot, else it will be a white spot in the image. So now the output image from the

image segmentation process is a black and white image.

Next, the image will be undergo feature extraction process. This process will do a dimensionality reduction that efficiently represent the region of interest (ROI) in an image. In this study, a bounding box was placed on the white dot in the image and then the coordinate of the bounding box in the form of (x-axis, y-axis, height, width). This coordinate is very important for the neural network algorithm later. Lastly, image classification process mainly used to recognize and categories one or more types of object in an image. However, image classification was not used in this study as we only have a single object to be detected in the image and it doesn't involve categorization of several objects in a single image. At the end of this algorithm, all of all images in the sample dataset were arranged in a table with their respective coordinate of the ROI.

To validate system, k-fold cross validation method was used to randomly partition the sample dataset into k equal sized subsamples. In this cross validation method, k-1 subsamples will be used as the training dataset to train the deep neural network while the remaining one subsamples left will be used to validate the trained network. As the result, there will be k trained network produced, and precision of the validation data each trained network will be take into account and an average precision will be obtained. In this study, 5 fold cross validation was used.

Next, deep neural network will be developed. In this study, Faster Region based Convolution Neural Network (Faster-RCNN) will be used. The basic architecture of Faster-RCNN is shown in Figure 4. The special part of Faster-RCNN than other type of deep neural network is that it have Region Proposal Network (RPN) that enable the system to take a shorter time to train the network. In RPN, the input image will go through a convolution network and output a sets of rectangular object proposals, each object proposal will come with an objectness score. (Ren et al. 2015)Then, for each object proposal, a ROI pooling layer extract a fixed-length feature vector from the feature map. The feature vector produced from the pooling layer fed into a fully connected layers and branch into two sibling output layers, the first one that produce softmax probability estimates over each object classes and second layer that will compute the four real-valued numbers for each of the object classes. This numbers are actually the same thing as the coordinate information we obtained from feature extraction that discussed earlier.

Figure 4. Basic Architecture of Faster RCNN

Source: (Girshick 2015)

In this study, faster RCNN had been developed with 3 main layers which is input layer, middle layer and output layer and 11 sub layers in total as shown in the Figure 5. A convolution layer convolves the input by moving the filters along the input vertically and horizontally. In this study, there are 64 filters with 10x10 size each were used in this layer. A 1x1 padding also used added to input edges. Besides that, this layer also compute the dot product of the weights and the input and lastly adding a bias term. Rectified Linear Unit Layer (ReLU layer) compute a threshold operation to each pixel in the input image, where by default any value more than 0 will be convert to 1 and 0 if less than 0. A 5x5 max pooling 2D layer with 2x2 stride was used. This layer divide the input into rectangular pooling regions to down-sampling, and computing maximum on each region of interest. A fully connected layer is similar to convolution layer where it multiplies the input by a weight matrix and a bias vector is added. A softmax layer, it applies a normalized exponential function to the input image. Lastly, classification output holds the information such as the size of the input and the class labels. [Harsh Pokhama. 2016]

To evaluate the system performance, precision-recall curve will be plotted to analyse the performance of the faster RCNN network. In this graph, x-axis is the recall or sensitivity of the system and y-axis is the precision or the true positive rate of the system. The precision and recall of the system can be computed from the formula

$$Precision = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_p}$$

$$Recall = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_n}$$

Where T_p = True Positive Value

F_p = False Positive Value

F_n = False Negative Value

True Positive means that the particular pixel is a laser spot, and the system successfully detected it as laser spot. False Positive means that the system had wrongly detect a particular pixel as the laser spot while False Negative indicate that the system had wrongly detect the location of the laser. The ideal precision-recall curve will have a curve that very near to the top right of the graph, so that the system achieved 100percent of precision and 100percent of recall or sensitivity.

Figure 5. The Layers Sequence Used in this Study

The first step is the pre-processing. The images are extracted to obtain three image with image primary colour Red, Green and Blue was obtained as shown in the Figure 6. As discussed earlier, only green image was chosen to do the further processing as in this image, the laser pointer are more easier to be distinguish by inspection. Therefore, the output image is only a black and white image.

Figure 6.a) Red Image b) Green Image c) Blue Image

Besides that, another reason of choosing green image is by looking at his histogram. The histogram of original image and the 3 primary colour was shown in the Figure 7. The histogram of the original image shows a there are a lot of different kind of colour existing in the image as there is no one sharp peak present. However, after converting to red image and green image, the histogram shows 2 sharp peaks. This indicates that most of the colour in the image had been normalised, most of the colour present in this image are more like a grayscale image. In blue image, the histogram shows the image had lost most of his characteristics and threshold value might be harder to obtain from this histogram.

Figure 7 The Histogram Of The Image in Different Form

Next, the green image will become a black and white image after thresholding segmentation as shown in the Figure 8 and lastly a bounding box is generated on the ROI as shown in Figure 9. The red bounding box indicates the location of the laser pointer in the original image. The information of the bounding box was then obtained in the form of [x-axis, y-axis, height, width]. This information is very important in further processing as this information provide the exact location of the laser pointer. This information was then arranged into a tables respective to the image. The constructed table is a 500x2 table that show the location of the image in my computer and 2nd column shows the bounding box information of the laser pointer in the bounding box.

Figure 8. The Input Image After Undergo Thresholding Segmentation

Figure 9. The Image with Red Box on the ROI

Next, the parts of sample dataset was used to train the network and the result obtained was used to plot a precision-recall curve. Since 5-fold cross validation was used, therefore, 5 results will be obtained and presented in precision-recall curve. All the results from all the 5 folds trained network was plotted in a single precision-recall curve as shown in the Figure 10. The average precision for all the 5 folds trained network are 0.95, 0.85, 0.45, 0.76, 0.64 respectively. Note that the curve of the second, third, fourth and fifth are just a straight line at precision=1 but it doesn't reach 100% at recall axis. Next, an average precision of all the 5 folds validation had been computed with an average precision of 0.73 as shown in the Figure 11. This overall precision shows that laser point had been successfully detected in most of the images by using the trained network.

Figure 10 Precision-Recall Curve of All The 5 Folds Trained Network

Figure 11 The Average Precision Obtained From 5 Trained Network

Conclusion

Two algorithm of laser pointer detection had been successfully developed. First, the general process of image processing had been developed for the purpose of preparing the sample dataset and validation after network had been trained. In this stage, the developed algorithm was assume to be a ground truth data that the RCNN result will be made compared with this algorithm to compute the average precision of the trained network on detecting the laser pointer in an image. As a result, the trained network shows 73 percent precision. Even though this result wasn't perfect, however some improvement can be made in the future such as hyperparameter optimization can be made to determine the best parameter such as number of layers, filter size and etc. that can be used to train the network. Besides that, bigger sample dataset size can be used to train the network to increase the performance of the network.

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